

Multiple efficient solutions generation

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1 Efficient solutions initial generation

1.1 Single criterion optimization

The MCO problem under consideration may be specified as

$$\max\{(q_1, \dots, q_n) : q \in A\} = \max\{(q_1, \dots, q_n) : q_i \leq f_i(x), x \in Q\} \quad (1)$$

At the initial phase of the MCA one needs to set the outcomes frame and generate some solutions. For this purpose the Pay-Off matrix is calculated, i.e. each objective is optimized separately. If these optimizations are regularized

$$\bar{q}^k \leftarrow \max\{q_k + \frac{\epsilon}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n q_i : q \in A\} \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

they provide also an initial collection of efficient solutions \bar{q}^k for $k = 1, \dots, n$.

In order to enforce better nadir estimation some additional calculations can be performed. Each such additional optimization generates some possibly different efficient solution.

One possibility to refine nadir evaluation is lexicographic regularization of single criterion optimizations (instead of regularization by the sum of criteria). This actually means, solving of $n!$ lexicographic problems for each permutation τ :

$$\text{lex max}\{(q_{\tau(1)}, \dots, q_{\tau(n)}) : q \in A\} \quad \tau \in \Pi(n) \quad (3)$$

For small n the lexicographic optimization can easily be approximated by single regularizations

$$\max\{\sum_{i=1}^n \epsilon^{i-1} q_{\tau(i)} : q \in A\} \quad \tau \in \Pi(n) \quad (4)$$

with small number $\epsilon > 0$. For larger n such a simplified approach is not implementable (due to limited computation precision) as well as the number of optimization instances $n!$ become impractically large.

While the lexicographic refinement is quite likely to improve the nadir evaluation (still taking into account only ‘corners’) it is rather unlikely to generate different enough solutions interesting for an initial sampling of the Pareto frontier.

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1.2 Multiple criteria optimization

Better estimation of the nadir vector one may usually get with simultaneous optimization of multiple criteria. For this purpose maxmin aggregation can be used for handling multiple criteria thus leading to optimization problems

$$\max\left\{\min_{1 \leq i \leq p} q_{\tau(i)} + \frac{\epsilon}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n q_i : q \in A\right\} \quad \tau \in \Pi(n); p = 2, \dots, n-1 \quad (5)$$

For $p = 1$ the above formula generate n standard corner solutions (2) while for $p = n$ the single regularized minimax solution. As the most promising limited number optimization problem one may consider the case of $p = n - 1$ which defines n problems (and efficient solutions)

$$\max\left\{\min_{i \neq k} q_i + \frac{\epsilon}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n q_i : q \in A\right\} \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (6)$$

For small n one may consider also $n(n-1)$ optimizations defined by pairs of criteria

$$\max\left\{\min\{q_{k'}, q_{ke}\} + \frac{\epsilon}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n q_i : q \in A\right\} \quad ke \neq k' = 1, \dots, n \quad (7)$$

1.3 Achievement function optimization

Sample compromise solutions can be generated with optimization of the achievement scalarizing function (ASF)

$$S(q, a, r) = \min_{1 \leq i \leq n} u_i(q_i, a_i, r_i) + \frac{\epsilon}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n u_i(q_i, a_i, r_i) \quad (8)$$

where a, r are vectors (composed of a_i, r_i , respectively) of aspiration and reservation levels respectively, and $u_i(q_i, a_i, r_i)$ are the corresponding Component Achievement Functions, which can be simply interpreted as nonlinear monotone transformations of q_i taking into account the information represented by a_i and r_i in such a way that $u_i(a_i, a_i, r_i) = \sigma^a \forall i$ and $u_i(r_i, a_i, r_i) = \sigma^r \forall i$. The ASF function is maximized.

The standard sample compromised efficient solution computed as the initial stage of analysis is the so-called neutral solution defined by the ASF optimization with the aspiration levels defined by utopia and the reservation levels defined by nadir (or proportionally placed within the utopia nadir interval)

$$\max\{S(q, q^u, q^n) : q \in A\} \quad (9)$$

One may try to extend the neutral solution to a family of diversified solutions using single criterion optimization similar to utopia computation. Let $s^* = \max\{S(q, q^u, q^n) : q \in A\}$ and let $0 < \mu < 1$ denote an acceptable decreasing factor for the worst achievement. One may generate n diversified efficient solutions around the neutral one by solving the following single objective optimizations:

$$\max\left\{q_k + \frac{\epsilon}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n q_i : q \in A, S(q, q^u, q^n) \geq \mu s^*\right\} \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (10)$$

The constraint on the ASF can be reformulated directly on outcomes $q_i \geq q_i^n + \mu s^* (q_i^u - q_i^n)$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$.

Alternatively, one may try to build an ASF optimization equivalent to (10) with appropriately defined reference point. For instance:

$$\max\{S(q, a, r) : q \in A\} \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (11)$$

with $r_i = q_i^n + \mu s^*(q_i^u - q_i^n)$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$ while $a_k = q_k^u$ and $a_i = q_i^n + s^*(q_i^u - q_i^n)$ for $i \neq k$.

2 Further generation of efficient solutions without preferences

2.1 Crowding distance measure

The crowding distance measure is used to evaluate nondominated population (say set N) with respect to possible elimination of some solutions. The crowding distance value of a solution provides an estimate of the density of solutions surrounding that solution. The crowding distance of point k is an estimate of the size of the largest hypercube enclosing k without including any other point thus evaluating the size of gap when eliminating the solution.

Crowding distance is calculated by first sorting the set of solutions in ascending objective function values. The crowding distance value of a particular solution is the distance of its two neighboring solutions. The boundary solutions which have the lowest and highest objective function values are given an infinite crowding distance values so that they are always selected. This process is done for each objective function. The final crowding distance value of a solution is computed by adding the entire individual crowding distance values in each objective function. The pseudocode of crowding distance computation can be specified as follows.

1. Get the number of nondominated solutions in the approximation set $p = |N| - 1$
2. Initialize distance
FOR $k = 0$ TO p DO $N[k].distance = 0$
3. Compute the crowding distance of each solution
For each objective i
Sort using each objective value $ON = sort(N.i)$, $num(k) =$ original index of efficient solution of the k ordered value ($ON[k] = N[num(k)].i$)
For $k = 1$ to $(p - 1)$ do $N[num(k)].distance = N[num(k)].distance + (ON[k + 1] - ON[k - 1])$
End objective loop
Set the maximum distance to the boundary points so that they are always selected
 $N[0].distance = N[p].distance = max_num$

2.2 Crowding distance for selection additional Reference Point

The distance of point k is an estimate of the size of the largest hypercube enclosing k without including any other point thus evaluating the size of gap when eliminating the solution. Therefore, this measure can also be (inversely) used to identify the largest hypercube gap within the set representation to be filled out with a new point. Certainly one cannot guarantee that any efficient point will belong to the specified hypercube. But there is no feasibility problem if one seeks a new reference point. It is important however that a hypercube must have a vertex at one of the efficient solutions.

Assume there are given given p efficient solutions. For each criterion i we have $p - 1$ intervals for placement of the i th coordinate of the reference point within the area defined by given efficient

solutions. If one would like to extend the search area outside the boundary of the given set of efficient points one should add artificial 2 points defined as tight bounds on the efficient solutions to be approximated $l_i \leq q_i \leq u_i \forall i$. One can easily find a place resulting in the largest crowding distance measure for this point when adding it into the set efficient solutions. Namely, one can find the largest hypercube executing the following algorithm.

Original Data: $N[k][i].val - k = 1, \dots, p$ (solutions), $i = 1, \dots, n$ -criteria

Variables:

$N[k].distance = 0$ - to generate total hypercube measure (the largest hypercube with vertex at $N[k]$)

$N[k][i].dev$ - the i th diameter size of the hypercube

$N[k][i].dir = 1$ or 0 - the i th diameter size of the hypercube (1 - increasing)

$N[k][i].dc$ - diameter decrease if changing the i th direction

$N[k][i].a$ - i th aspiration level related to the (largest) hypercube with vertex at $N[k]$

$N[k][i].r$ - i th reservation level related to the (largest) hypercube with vertex at $N[k]$

1. Initialization:

Sorting increasingly solution values for each criterion separately:

$ON[k][i].val$ - sorted values for $k = 1, \dots, p$

$ON[k][i].ind$ - solution index of sorted outcomes, i.e., $ON[k][i].val = N[ON[k][i].ind][i].val$

2. Calculation I:

FOR $i = 1$ TO n DO

BEGIN

$N[ON[1][i].ind][i].dev = ON[2][i].val - ON[1][i].val$

$N[ON[1][i].ind][i].dir = 1$

$N[ON[1][i].ind][i].dc = ON[2][i].val - ON[1][i].val$

FOR $k = 2$ TO $p - 1$ DO

IF ($ON[k+1][i].val - ON[k][i].val > ON[k][i].val - ON[k-1][i].val$)

BEGIN

$N[ON[k][i].ind][i].dev = ON[k+1][i].val - ON[k][i].val$

$N[ON[k][i].ind][i].dir = 1$

$N[ON[k][i].ind][i].dc = ON[k+1][i].val - 2 * ON[k][i].val + ON[k-1][i].val$

END ELSE

BEGIN

$N[ON[k][i].ind][i].dev = ON[k][i].val - ON[k-1][i].val$

$N[ON[k][i].ind][i].dir = 0$

$N[ON[k][i].ind][i].dc = -ON[k+1][i].val + 2 * ON[k][i].val - ON[k-1][i].val$

END

$N[ON[p][i].ind][i].dev = ON[p][i].val - ON[p-1][i].val$

$N[ON[p][i].ind][i].dir = 0$

$N[ON[p][i].ind][i].dc = ON[p][i].val - ON[p-1][i].val$

END

3. Efficiency verification:

FOR $k = 1$ TO p DO

IF ($\sum_{i=1}^n N[k][i].dir = n$ OR $\sum_{i=1}^n N[k][i].dir = 0$)

BEGIN

FIND $mindc = \min_{i=1, \dots, n} N[k][i].dc$ and $imindc$ the corresponding index i

$N[k][imindc].dev = N[k][imindc].dev - mindc$

$N[k][imindc].dir = 1 - N[k][imindc].dir$

END

4. Final computation:
 - FOR $k = 1$ TO p DO
 - BEGIN
 - COMPUTE final measure, e.g.,
 - $N[k].distance = \sum_{i=1}^n N[k][i].dev$ for sum/average diameter measure
 - $N[k].distance = \max_{i=1, \dots, n} N[k][i].dev$ for max diameter measure
 - Combined or other functions (OWA)
 - Define A/R levels for selected hypercube:
 - FOR $i = 1$ TO n DO
 - BEGIN
 - $N[k][i].a = N[k][i].val + N[k][i].dir * N[k][i].dev$
 - $N[k][i].r = N[k][i].val - (1 - N[k][i].dir) * N[k][i].dev$
 - END
 - END
5. Hypercube(s) selection:
 - IF (single selection)
 - $kmax = \max_{k=1, \dots, p} N[k].distance$, let $ikmax$ the corresponding index
 - aspiration and reservation levels defined by $N[ikmax][i].a$ and $N[ikmax][i].r$, respectively
 - ELSE (multiple selection)
 - Select any number of largest (possible all) among p hypercubes and their reference points ($N[ikmax][i].a$ and $N[ikmax][i].r$)
 - Note that some hypercubes may have very small size $N[k].distance$
 - Some hypercubes may be identical or close, some filtering must be need for multiple selection case.

The above procedure should be essentially considered for a single reference point introduction and finding the corresponding new efficient solution expanding the current set (approximation). When looking for simultaneous placement of a few reference points one may assume the first reference point as a tentative extension of the efficient set thus finding the second largest hypercube etc. Exactly, the point $(a + r)/2$ or $r + \varepsilon$ can be used for this purpose.

3 Neighbor solutions hypercubes

3.1 Algorithm

Instead of constructing hypercubes on the grid of sorted outcomes one may try to analyze hypercubes generated by all possible pairs of efficient solutions. For such simplified hypercubes one may seek the m largest hypercubes simultaneously.

Again, assume there are given tight bounds on the efficient solutions to be approximated $l_i \leq q_i \leq u_i \forall i$ and there is given p efficient solutions.

Original Data: $N[k][i].val - k = 1, \dots, p$ (solutions), $i = 1, \dots, n$ -criteria

Variables:

$H[k, k'].distance$ - hypercube measure

$H[k, k'][i].a$ - the i th aspiration level (upper level) for the hypercube

$H[k, k'][i].r$ - the i th reservation level (lower level) for the hypercube

HLIST - list of the currently m largest hypercubes

COMMENT: structure H need not be defined for all pairs but at least m of them will be stored

1. Initialization: Initialize $HLIST = \emptyset$
2. Hypercubes generation:


```

FOR  $k = 1$  TO  $p$  DO
FOR  $k' = k + 1$  TO  $p$  DO
BEGIN
Hypercube definition:
FOR  $i = 1$  TO  $n$  DO
IF ( $N[k][i].val > N[k'][i].val$ )
BEGIN
 $H[k, k'][i].a = N[k][i].val$ ;  $H[k, k'][i].r = N[k'][i].val$ 
END ELSE
BEGIN
 $H[k, k'][i].r = N[k][i].val$ ;  $H[k, k'][i].a = N[k'][i].val$ 
END
Measure calculation, e.g.,
 $H[k, k'].distance = \sum_{i=1}^n (H[k, k'][i].a - H[k, k'][i].r)$  for sum/average diameter measure
 $H[k, k'].distance = \max_{i=1, \dots, n} (H[k, k'][i].a - H[k, k'][i].r)$  for max diameter measure
Combined or other measure functions if applied
Checking the result and abandon this hypercube if too small (CONTINUE)
Checking direct neighborhoodness:
FOR  $l = 1$  TO  $p$ ,  $l \neq k$ ,  $l \neq k'$  DO
BEGIN
FAIL=1
IF ( $N[l].val \cong N[k].val \mid N[l].val \cong n[k'].val$ ) {FAIL=0; CONTINUE( $l$ )}
FOR  $i = 1$  TO  $n$  DO
FAIL =  $isinside(l, H[k, k'])$ 
IF (FAIL) abandon this hypercube BREAK( $l$ )
END( $l$ )
IF (FAIL==0) update HLIST with current hypercube
END( $k, k'$ )

```
3. Sort HLIST with respect to decreasing distances/sizes
Eliminate too similar hypercubes. Select specified number of the largest.

Function $isinside(l, H)$

ushort $isinside(\text{solution } l, \text{cube } H)$

```

{ int i;
FOR  $i = 1$  TO  $n$  DO
IF ( $N[l][i].val < H[i].r - \varepsilon$ 
OR  $N[l][i].val > H[i].a + \varepsilon$ ) return(0);
return(1);
}
```

3.2 Dimension expansion

One have to notice that the algorithm may generate a degenerate hypercube (dimension less than n) with some $H[k, k'][i].r = H[k, k'][i].a$ thus requiring a special technique to define reference points. There is an opportunity to expand degenerate hypercubes with procedure similar to that based

on the crowding distance, i.e. using the grid of criteria values taken on the set N or directly placing the largest possible hypercube within the remaining directions. The former is a procedure where we examine not used criteria directions and identify the closest objective value on the set N independently whether the other coordinates of the solution fit the hypercube dimension already stated (positive diameters). In the latter while analyzing not used criteria directions and identifying the closest objective value we examine only those solutions from N for which the other coordinates of the solution fit the hypercube dimension already stated (positive diameters). If there is no such a solution the corresponding lower limit l_i or upper limit u_i is used. Certainly the expansion procedure is applicable only for such hypercube $H[k, k']$ that $\min_{i=1, \dots, n} (H[k, k'][i].a - H[k, k'][i].r) < \varepsilon$ (0 for at least one dimension).

The dimension expansion algorithm for hypercube $H[k, k']$ can be stated as the following procedure for building a list $HLIST(k, k')$ of expanding hypercubes defined by various efficient solutions $N[ke]$. To generate an expansion hypercube the solution must fit all nonzero edges of the current hypercube.

```

FOR ke = 1 TO p, ke ≠ k, ke ≠ k' DO
BEGIN
BEGIN(Solution verification)
FAILBIS=0
FOR i = 1 TO n DO
IF (H[k, k'][i].a - H[k, k'][i].r) > ε % If active (nonzero) dimension
{ IF (N[ke][i].val < H[k, k'][i].r - ε or N[l][i].val > H[k, k'][i].a + ε) { FAILBIS=1; BREAK(i) } }
END(Solution verification)
IF (FAILBIS==0)
BEGIN(potential hypercube)
Hypercube definition:
FOR i = 1 TO n DO
BEGIN
H[ke][i].r = H[k, k'][i].r
H[ke][i].a = H[k, k'][i].a
IF (N[ke][i].val > H[k, k'][i].a)
BEGIN
H[ke][i].a = N[ke][i].val
H[ke][i].r = H[k, k'][i].r
END ELSE
IF (N[ke][i].val < H[k, k'][i].r)
BEGIN
H[ke][i].r = N[ke][i].val
H[ke][i].a = H[k, k'][i].a
END
END(i)
Checking direct neighborhoodness:
FOR l = 1 TO p, l ≠ k, l ≠ k', l ≠ ke DO
BEGIN
FAIL=1
IF (N[l].val ≅ N[k].val || N[l].val ≅ n[k'].val || N[l].val ≅ n[ke].val) { FAIL=0; CONTINUE(l) }
FAIL = isinside(l, H[ke])
IF (FAIL) abandon this hypercube BREAK(l)

```

END(l)
 IF (FAIL==0)
 BEGIN
 Measure calculation, e.g., $H[ke].distance = \sum_{i=1}^n (H[ke][i].a - H[ke][i].r)$ for sum diameter measure
 $H[ke].distance = \max_{i=1, \dots, n} (H[ke][i].a - H[ke][i].r)$ for max diameter measure
 Combined or other measure functions if applied
 Update $HLLIST(k, k')$ with $H[ke]$ if not too small
 END
 END(potential hypercube)
 END(ke)

3.3 Progress measurement

There are several possible ways to measure a progress while generating more efficient solution. Although it is not easy to define a measure taking into account uniformity of the solutions distribution. This requires some external uniform grid and a measure of equal feeling this grid.

While generating new solution by the neighbor solutions hypercubes generation, one may measure the progress by the sizes (distances) of a few largest hypercubes identified after the iteration (in the subsequent iteration). Recall, that the list is sorted according to decreasing cube sizes. Let m (say $m = 10$) denote the number of the largest cubes analyzed. We will count vectors of m components:

M[0] – the largest size $HLLIST[0].size$

M[1] – average of two largest dimensions $(HLLIST[0].size + HLLIST[1].size)/2$

M[j] – average of $j + 1$ largest dimensions $(\sum_{l=0}^j HLLIST[l].size)/j$

This provides us with a multidimensional measure allowing more detailed progress analysis. Although for quick reporting one may focus on M[0] and/or M[4], M[9].

One may also calculate a total (average) measure

$$M = \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} M[j]$$

or any

$$M = \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} w_j HLLIST[j].size, \quad w_0 > \dots > w_{m-1}, \quad \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} w_j = 1$$

representing the ordered weighted average where the largest size is more weighted than the second largest and so on. For instance,

$$w_j = \frac{2(m-j)}{m(m+1)}$$

4 Generation more solutions for given preferences

During the interactive analysis an efficient solution computed the ASF (8) optimization according to given aspiration and reservation levels

$$\max\{S(q, a, r) : q \in A\} \tag{12}$$

4.1 ASF modifications

One may try to extend the found solution to a family of diversified solutions using single criterion optimization similar to utopia computation. Let $s^* = \max\{S(q, a, r) : q \in A\}$ and let $0 < \mu < 1$ denote an acceptable decreasing factor for the worst achievement. One may generate n diversified efficient solutions around the neutral one by solving the following single objective optimizations:

$$\max\{q_k + \frac{\epsilon}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n q_i : q \in A, S(q, a, r) \geq \mu s^*\} \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (13)$$

The constraint on the ASF can be reformulated directly on outcomes $q_i \geq q_i^n + \mu s^*(q_i^u - q_i^n)$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$.

While using an absolute decreasing constant δ the same problem can be formulated as

$$\max\{q_k + \frac{\epsilon}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n q_i : q \in A, S(q, a, r) \geq s^* - \delta\} \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (14)$$

and it may be implemented as maximization of the ASF while using the constant δ to shift the values of all CAFs except of the k th.

Alternatively, one may try to build an ASF optimization equivalent to (13) with appropriately defined reference point. For instance:

$$\max\{S(q, \bar{a}, \bar{r}) : q \in A\} \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (15)$$

with $\bar{r}_i = r_i + \mu s^*(a_i - r_i)$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$ while $\bar{a}_k = q_k^u$ and $\bar{a}_i = r_i + s^*(a_i - r_i)$ for $i \neq k$.

4.2 Local hypercubes generation

Having generated a solution $N[\bar{k}]$ according to given preferences one may try to search for alternative close solutions by examining preferences generated by hypercubes raised with solutions and any other efficient solution. This require application of the procedure from Section 3 with external loop reduced to a single solution, i.e., with replacement of

Hypercubes generation:

FOR $k = 1$ TO p DO

FOR $k' = k + 1$ TO p DO

with

Hypercubes generation:

FOR $k = \bar{k}$

FOR $k' = 1$ TO p , $k' \neq k$ DO

5 State of the art

5.1 Assumptions

We are focusing on:

1. Linear programming problems
2. We are focusing on optimization problems with several of criteria.
3. The computation time of linear programming problem is up to 0.5 hour.

5.2 Initial representation of Pareto frontier

The basic characteristic points:

- Utopia
- Nadir
- Neutral solution

The methods of finding utopia and nadir points based on solving additional optimization problems are presented in paper [1]. Exact methods can be applied for small number of criteria. In case of more advanced problem formulation evolutionary algorithms can be applied [2, 3]. Neutral solution can be calculated by setting as an aspiration point utopia point and as reservation point nadir point.

5.3 Global representation of Pareto frontier

We can distinguish the following methods:

- Approximation of Pareto set
- Representation of Pareto set

In the paper [4] various approaches to approximation of the efficient set is reviewed. In this paper the following classes of approximation methods are considered: approximation by points, linear, quadratic, cubic functions (or piecewise) and other functions and sets.

Pareto set can be represented by a discrete set of Pareto optimal solution. Denote by \hat{Q} Pareto-optimal set and A the representation set of \hat{Q} .

One of procedures to find discrete representations of the efficient set can be found in [5] [6].

Not cited reference (from the bib-file, citation added by MM): [7].

5.4 Local representation of Pareto frontier considering preference information

5.5 The quality of representation

There is a need of assessment of various representations of Pareto set by a set of nondominated solutions. In the paper [8] there is overview of various quality measures of representation. Sayin00

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